

Innovative potential of management conceptual model issues

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Abstract- In this article, a number of issues that need to be resolved before the start of innovative processes before the enterprises introducing innovative innovations are thoroughly analyzed, and conceptual approaches in the innovation management system are highlighted.

Key words - conceptual, innovation, scientific-technical, financial-economic, license , know-how , marketing ,

Conceptual approach means starting and implementing the most basic idea, an innovative process with specific priorities. The development of our country, in general, the role and importance of innovations, scientific and technical achievements in increasing the efficiency of social production in the economy is extremely great. 70 percent of the increase in the efficiency of social production is ensured by technical factors - products, technological innovations and updates.

At the same time, it is worth saying that innovations can be dangerous for many enterprises, scientific and technical complexes, organizations, as well as individual sectors that are currently operating effectively. Because they create and assimilate various innovations, they may not be able to see the consequences of these scientific and technical achievements, they may not be able to maintain the necessary level of innovative activity and directions. As a result, in most cases, despite efforts to ensure efficiency based on the results of innovative solutions, financial and economic indicators may fall, market share may be lost, and ultimately, a crisis may occur.

As a result, it can be concluded that the deterioration of the financial and economic situation of enterprises and the small sector does not occur only due to the lack of innovation. The problem here is not innovation itself. Perhaps, in the first place, it is

the effective management of news and its orientation to a specific indicator or indicators. The following indicators confirm our opinion. Only 10% of innovative developments lead to commercial success, the remaining 90% are unsuccessful developments.

There are a number of issues that need to be addressed before starting innovation processes for businesses that are innovating, including:[1]

- the innovation process all duties and stages

in the enterprise solution reach

- innovative of developments how much part different organizations by fulfillment to determine

- placed to the table licenses or "know - how " to the hand input the way with reach

- innovative affairs expenses work to issue or to marketing expendable common to expenses higher than has been efficiency provide get

- work release and to marketing spend done expenses short in term much efficient activity walking of the enterprise long time during efficiency guarantee get

News different types of districts account will receive if so , this to questions answer to find more it is difficult . To these enterprises in a comprehensive manner to be considered if or them different level merging for certain to priorities directed develop a clear concept developed to be need of the world many in countries last until now innovations of management all levels their to the product orientation , that is , news work to issue directed observation possible was (Chart 1). To the concept according to , innovative the process to the product orientation represents , that is , of the consumer work to the issuer relatively position very weak will be This on the ground the news create , master and to distribute related q has been all conditions work issuer puts

In the context of economic liberalization, work release structural again

construction and social of needs complication consumer positions less to be strengthened take will come That's it remember catch The idea of marketing should be theirs such change point of view in terms of take than news own still final goal not only consumer needs from awareness consists of Although , last in years consumer i - of requirements known level being created in the news on the contrary finding but still this positive process the innovator , that is , the " initiator" of innovations to the consumer does not approximate [2].

Drawing 1

From this come It turns out that the researcher is still a designer and technologist from the market separate remains They still are of innovation commerce point of view in terms of potential and their personal and work release needs satisfy to get yes yes they can't give . That's why for also , alternative new conceptual approach necessary

Such approach innovative knowledge consumers needs to satisfy orientation process as is considered . New product only to the technology carrier becoming a profession reached form while only technology is being met need with from connected after manifestation will be Result one is a novelty product although - we , this on the ground him work of the issuer innovative potential to business goals transform character about imagination how long that it has changed we will see , because the second approach future of the consumer needs subjugated . News indicators future market needs when connected failed news percentage decreases , because, their most of them such of the related cli lack of with is determined .

Innovations efficiency commerce to the achievement many factors with effect does , of them the most the main ones :[3]

- to the market orientation ;
- innovative projects choose get and please efficient system ;
- projects efficient manage and control to do
- creative ideas source ;
- of the organization to the news flexibility , effectiveness ;
- to the news resistance show

This is the most important aspect - to the market get directions with directly depend That is , put from tasks one is the field of ITTKI constant between marketing with contact to the road is to put .B u on the ground communicative difficulties and enterprises organizational structure with depends problems They are employees of ITTKI and marketing specialists between efficient relationships to the road to put help not giving , but hindering too does

As you know , the news create idea usually market from needs come comes out or ITTKI units inside is born These two out of the way which one more efficient the fact that about most of the time dependent a- against thoughts is reported . Market economy developed countries practice that's it shows that the news base , organization who does all 25-35 % of ideas are ITTKI divisions inside appear will be Theirs sure ratio how no matter what , that's it obviously , ITTKI is both marketing and of ideas main source being service does , to development and most of them cases weak communications and mutually of understanding lack of hindrance does News create of the idea this two creative source to each other against to put not so much right not Technical aspects and to the market related q aspects to each other productive tie up necessary for this and services between near connections to the road to put through reach can

In conclusion, k orib developed conceptual to the models relatively this that's

it means that every both approach , that is , " To the product orientation ” and “ To the market orientation ” is known level own place and importance have State economic of development , networks and enterprises of the situation present stage second conceptual management - to the market directed priority is given However that's it despite this without too creative of ideas two source between certain ratio storage it is necessary " To the product orientation ” conceptual abandon the approach , the market to relations transition necessity r okach to do to the goal according to not with this together innovations of management all levels is wrong . These views new of developments decreased innovation scientific and technical level to decrease and in the end , the country , its regions are also separate networks and of enterprises innovative potential development from the point of view behind to stay take will come

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